

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Enhance Brand Awareness for Wisata Murah Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Tourism is one of the industries most impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. As the virus recedes, the tourism industry is experiencing a revival, resulting in increased competition. Nevertheless, numerous businesses are unable to regain their pre-pandemic positions. Wisata Murah Indonesia is among the companies facing this situation due to the company's lack of brand awareness. This research aims to raise awareness and develop a new marketing strategy for Wisata Murah Indonesia in order to boost revenue. This research uses two methods of analysis, namely the qualitative method and the quantitative method to conduct internal and external analysis. The outcomes were then used as the foundation for a SWOT analysis, which was followed by a TOWS analysis and a QSPM analysis to identify possible implementation strategies. This analysis results in a new business strategy to increase revenue at Wisata Murah Indonesia is to create affordable, trend-based special tour packages and to add passport and visa-making services so that customers are attracted by the convenience of travel. Additionally, raise awareness by conducting online and offline promotions. Online promotions include collaborating with influencers and adding new marketing channels, namely TikTok and YouTube. Offline promotion is by making tour packages with special prices or discounts for offline purchases, such as at the Travel Fair. Wisata Murah Indonesia can also improve their brand reputation to increase customer loyalty and potential customers.

KEYWORDS: Advertising, Brand Awareness, Intention to Buy, Social Media Marketing, Word of Mouth.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 had a significant impact on various sectors, including the tourism sector. The number of international tourist arrivals worldwide experienced a significant decline in 2020. It plummeted from the previous number of 1,465.46 million to a mere 406.88 million [1]. However, as the pandemic situation improved and restrictions were lifted, the tourism sector started to recover in all countries, including Indonesia. In 2022, the number of domestic tourists increased by 19.82% compared to 2021 and grew by 1.76% compared to 2019 [2]. This number has exceeded the number of visits before the pandemic. The growth in travel activities has had a huge positive impact on the Indonesian tour and travel business. One of the main impact obtained is an increase in demand for tour and travel services. With the growing number of tourists, many of them want assistance in preparing their vacation, including transportation, lodging, and tourist activities [3]. Technological advancements also have an impact on the growth of travel activity. The rising adoption of technology and digital platforms simplifies the travel process for individuals. More and more people are utilizing websites, travel applications, and social media platforms to access information, reserve tickets, and arrange their journeys.

In line with the development of travel activities, the competition for tour and travel companies in Indonesia is also getting tougher. Many tour and travel companies are trying to gain limited market share by offering more competitive prices or attractive travel packages. In addition, a new phenomenon called "revenge travel" has emerged, in which people really want to travel after being isolated at home during a pandemic.

One of the companies facing challenges in the tourism business competition is Wisata Murah Indonesia. Wisata Murah Indonesia is a company that provides travel services related to tourism, such as purchasing airplane tickets, hotels, transportation and domestic and international tour packages. The condition of the company's income is still low compared to pre-pandemic levels. This is due to people who are still less aware of this company. The company is still not optimal in doing marketing such as by doing advertising, word of mouth and social media marketing activities. Therefore, this research aims to raise brand awareness by developing a new marketing strategy for Wisata Murah Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand awareness refers to consumer's ability to identify brands in different situations, demonstrated by their brand recognition or recall [4]. Advertising is a cost-effective method of delivering messages, whether the objective is to shape brand preferences or provide information [4]. Advertising plays a crucial role for companies in promoting their products and capturing consumers' attention to drive purchases, thereby influencing consumers' perception of a brand [5]. When an advertisement successfully captures consumers' attention, it enhances their ability to recall and recognize the advertised brand or product [6]. Word of mouth is a communication method involving the sharing of recommendations, either individually or in groups, regarding a product or service [4]. Consumers who are satisfied with a brand are more likely to tell others about the brand, so that more and more people are aware of the brand [7]. Social media marketing can be defined as an interactive marketing communication activity that takes place between businesses and their customers and vice versa with the goal of increasing sales of products and services offered by these businesses. Engaging in social media marketing activities enables businesses to grow brand awareness and cultivate a favorable brand image by facilitating interactions with potential and existing customers [8]. Purchase intention is the behaviour of consumers who desire to make a purchase of a product [4]. It is crucial that customers identify brands and contemplate making another purchase [9].

METHODOLOGY

First step in this research is the exploration of business issues. Data for this business issue were obtained through interviews. Following that, the research was carried on with an internal and external analysis. Internal analysis is used with Marketing Mix Analysis, STP (Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning) Analysis, and VRIO (Value, Rarity, Inimitable, and Organization) Analysis. While, external analysis is used with PESTEL Analysis, Porter 5 Forces Analysis, Competitor Analysis, and Consumer Analysis. The results of the internal and external analysis are used as the basis for the SWOT Analysis, then create a strategy with the TOWS Analysis and select an alternative strategy by conducting a QSPM. This study used a quantitative method by distributing questionnaires to 200 respondents, then the data will be processed using PLS-SEM.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Customer Analysis

1) Validity and Reliability Test

Validity test can use the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). If the AVE value is > 0.5 , it can be said that the indicator has good convergent validity. Composite Reliability is a group of indicators that measure a variable having good composite reliability based on a composite reliability score. The results of the composite reliability test are said to be good if the value is > 0.6 . Cronbach's Alpha is an indicator group that measures a variable having good composite reliability based on the alpha coefficient value. The results of the composite reliability test are said to be good if the value is > 0.7 . The following is the result of validity and reliability test.

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test

variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Advertising	0.861	0.905	0.705
Word of Mouth	0.918	0.948	0.859
Social Media Marketing	0.838	0.903	0.756
Brand Awareness	0.813	0.877	0.641
Intention to Buy	0.765	0.858	0.670

2) R-Square

The R Square test is a goodness fit model test. Where R Square is used for the dependent variable, dependent variable or endogenous variable. The following is the result of R-Square.

Table 2. R Table

Dependent Variable	R Square
Brand Awareness	0.423
Intention to Buy	0.517

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the R Square value of the brand awareness variable in this study is 0,423. The R Square value indicates that brand awareness can be explained by 42,3% by advertising, word of mouth, and social media marketing variables. While the remaining 57,7% is explained by other variables not used in this study. Furthermore, the R Square value of the intention to buy variable in this study is 0,517. The R Square value shows that the intention to buy can be explained by 51,7% by the brand awareness variable. While the remaining 48.3% is explained by other variables not used in this study.

3) T-Statistic and P-Value

The t-statistic values generated from the bootstrap resampling technique will be compared with the t-table values. The hypothesis is accepted if the t-statistic value is higher than the t-table value, and vice versa. T-table of this research is 1.96. P value is used to determine whether the variable is significant or not. A variable will be said to be significant if the p value is < 0.05.

Table 3. T-Statistic and P-Value

	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Values
Advertising -> Brand Awareness	2.079	0.038
Brand Awareness -> Intention to Buy	18.319	0.000
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness	5.378	0.000
Word of Mouth -> Brand Awareness	2.004	0.045

Based on the table above, it can be seen that all statistical T values > 1.96, it can be concluded that the relationship between latent variables is significant (positive effect). Also, it can be seen that all P values are below 0.05, so it can be concluded that all variables have a significant influence so that all hypotheses can be accepted.

B. SWOT Analysis

- Strength (Based on Internal Analysis)
 - 1) Has departure points in Jakarta, Surabaya and Yogyakarta
 - 2) Tour packages that are more affordable than competitors
 - 3) Has many choices of tour packages domestically or internationally
 - 4) Flexible Payment Procedure
 - 5) Has qualified human resources
- Weakness (Based on Internal Analysis)
 - 1) Lack of Awareness
 - 2) Promotion in digital media has not been maximally carried out
 - 3) Offline promotions have not been carried out after the pandemic 4) The commission is only given on the second trip
- Opportunities (Based on External Analysis)
 - 1) Positive influence of advertising, word of mouth, and social media marketing towards brand awareness 2) Positive influence of brand awareness towards intention to buy
 - 3) The trend for traveling is increasing every year
 - 4) The elimination of all PPKM policies in Indonesia to make it easier for people to travel more
 - 5) The strengthening of the rupiah encourages traveling abroad

- 6) The number of internet users in Indonesia is increasing
- 7) Indonesia's economic growth is positive, with an increasing number of consumers who can afford to travel and tour
- Threats (Based on External Analysis)
 - 1) The strength of Indonesian passports has decreased this year
 - 2) The development of Online Travel Agent (OTA) which is increasing every year
 - 3) High competition in the tour and travel industry
 - 4) Customers have the power to influence prices because of the many alternative travel agents in the industry
 - 5) The threat of new entrants is high due to the increasing number of tourists every year
 - 6) The threat of substitute products is high because tourists can travel without having to use a travel agent

C. TOWS Analysis

- S-O Strategy
 - 1) Make a new tour package based on the growing trend and adjusted to a competitive price (S2, S3, O3, O4, O5, O8)
- W-O Strategy
 - 1) Improving services such as adding services for making passports and visas (S3, S5, T1, T3, T7) 2) Build customer loyalty by strengthening brand reputation (S1, S2, S3, S4, T5, T6)
- S-T Strategy
 - 1) Optimizing promotion on digital media by adding new marketing channels, namely Tiktok and Youtube (W1, W2, O1, O2, O6)
 - 2) Collaborate with Influencers (W1, W2, O1, O2, O3, O6)
- S-T Strategy
 - 1) Provide tour packages with special prices or discounts for purchases made offline (W3, W4, T6, T7)

D. Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) Analysis

The QSPM analysis is used to determine the most suitable business strategy for a company based on an examination of internal and external factors. The following is the result of QSPM Analysis.

Table 4. QSPM Result.

No	Strategy	QSPM Score
1	Collaborate with Influencers	7,844
2	Optimizing promotion on digital media by adding new marketing channels, namely Tiktok and Youtube	7,748
3	Make a new tour package based on the growing trend and adjusted to a competitive price	7,738
4	Build customer loyalty by strengthening brand reputation	7,522
5	Provide tour packages with special prices or discounts for purchases made offline	6,659
6	Improving services such as adding services for making passports and visas	4,399

Based on the results of the QSPM analysis above, it can be seen that those with the highest QSPM Scores are strategy collaborate with influencers, so it can be concluded that this strategy is the strategy most prioritized by the company.

E. Marketing Strategy

- Collaborate with Influencers
Wisata Murah Indonesia can use the services of Influencers to participate in promoting on Digital Media. Influencers will take part in trips conducted by company, then later they will document their trips and will upload them on their respective social media accounts.

- Optimizing promotion on digital media by adding new marketing channels, namely Tiktok and Youtube
TikTok and Youtube are among the top social media applications that are popularly used by the public in finding out vacation destinations. Company can carry out promotions by creating content about the attractive holiday destinations it offers. Emphasize unique selling points and value proposition to differentiate from competitors so that more people are aware of the company's existence.
- Make a new tour package based on the growing trend and adjusted to a competitive price
The ability of Wisata Murah Indonesia, which has many tour packages at low prices, can be used to continue to create and upgrade new tour packages according to traveling trends and current conditions. The abolition of the PPKM policy and the strengthening of the rupiah exchange rate can encourage customers' desire to travel abroad. Examples of tour packages that are made can be according to the season, namely a tour for spring and viewing cherry blossoms in Japan, a tour to feel Christmas in Europe, and so on.
- Build customer loyalty by strengthening brand reputation
Wisata Murah Indonesia can take advantage of the company's strengths to further enhance brand reputation and highlight the company's points of differentiation. Companies can provide an extraordinary customer experience and meet expectations. Then, provide a loyalty program for customers who want to make repeat orders. The advantages of the loyalty program are getting discounts, getting more payment flexibility, and so on.
- Provide tour packages with special prices or discounts for purchases made offline
Wisata Murah Indonesia can offer prices or discounts for customers who make purchases offline, such as purchases at a travel fair. This also applies to customers who are using Wisata Murah Indonesia services for the first time. This can encourage customers to use Wisata Murah Indonesia because customers already get a complete tour package at a low price so that the company is expected to be able to compete in the industry.
- Improving services such as adding services for making passports and visas
Wisata Murah Indonesia can add services for making passports and visas for every customer who wants to travel abroad. This will make it easier for every customer who has just left the country for the first time so that it still encourages customers to continue to want to travel abroad even though the strength of the Indonesian passport is weakening. Apart from that, this service for making passports and visas can also solve problems with the development of OTAs because customers don't have to bother taking care of it alone.

CONCLUSION

A suitable marketing strategy to increase revenue from Wisata Murah Indonesia is to make special tour packages based on developing trends at affordable prices and also add passport and visa making services so that customers are interested in the convenience of traveling. Apart from that, Wisata Murah Indonesia can also increase brand awareness by promoting both online and offline. Online promotions include collaborating with Influencers and adding new marketing channels, namely TikTok and Youtube so that more and more audiences are familiar with Wisata Murah Indonesia through social media. In addition, company can also carry out offline promotions by creating tour packages with special prices or discounts for offline purchases, such as at the Travel Fair. In addition, Wisata Murah Indonesia can also improve their brand reputation to increase customer loyalty and potential customers.

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